

TIGRAY WATER WORKS STUDY, DESIGN AND SUPERVISION ENTERPRISE

HEC-SSP TRAINING MANUAL

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1. Introduction

Every stream or river has instances of extremely augmented flow. Therefore, when designing engineered hydrologic systems, it is imperative that Water Resources Engineers can attempt to understand the temperament of these flows and storms by applying statistics to the recorded flows to determine hydrologic extremes. These values, such as the 100-year flood, assist a designer in enumerating the flow parameters around which a spillway or Diversion weir must be built in order to minimize risk. We will use HEC-SSP program to analyze the hydro-metrological data extremes.

2. Installing HEC-SSP

1. Download HEC-SSP software from <http://www.hec.usace.army.mil/>
2. Run the installation to your PC, after installation has completed, you can run the software. The first time you start HEC-SSP you will be asked to accept the license agreement. Read the terms and conditions (scroll to end of the box) and accept these.

3. Create New Study

3. Open up HEC-SSP. Under the File tab, select New Study in order to create the template used in this case study.

- Give your study Name and Description as in example, HEC-SSP Exercise, HEC-SSP Exercise Case Study @ Maychew respectively and place it in a directory where you will be able to find it. Make sure to set Unit System to SI and not English, once these have been established, click OK.

- Adding a Background Map by default, when you start a new project in HEC-SSP a default map window (called Base Map) will open in the Desktop window. Having a background map is optional in HEC-SSP. Not having a map does not prevent the user from importing and entering data, or performing an analysis and viewing results. The map is mostly a visual aid of the study area. Additionally, when you bring in gage data you can enter the map coordinates of the gage and it will show up on the map. The user must supply a coordinate system other than X-Y (i.e. Geographic) for imported gage data to be displayed properly. Once a gage is located on the map you can right click on it to open a shortcut menu for viewing the data, or graphing and tabulating the results.

To add a map layer to the default map, go to the **Maps** menu and select **Add Map Layers**. When this option is selected a file chooser window will appear, allowing the user to select map layers to bring into the map. The **Create Copy** option on the window will make a copy of the selected map and place it in the Maps subdirectory within the study folder.

Currently, the HEC-SSP software can load the following types of map layers: United States Geologic Survey (USGS) DLG, AutoCAD DXF, shape file, Raster Image, USGS DEM, Arc Info DEM, ASCII NetTIN, and Mr Sid.

An example map is shown in Figure 3-1. This map contains a shape file of Met Station in Maychew town.

Figure 3-1: Maychew Met. Station Base Map.

4. Create Excel Data

6. Create a new XLS file (Excel 97 format) with two columns hydro-meteorological data to be imported

	A	B	C
1	Rainfall for Maychew Station		
2	2-Aug-1992	54.1	
3	27-Aug-1993	92.1	
4	30-Sep-1994	68.1	
5	19-Aug-1995	58.6	
6	11-Aug-1996	51.8	
7	23-Oct-1997	30.8	
8	14-May-1998	89.5	
9	17-Aug-1999	50.8	
10	29-Oct-2000	63	
11	19-Aug-2001	44.3	
12	6-Oct-2002	45.5	
13	26-Mar-2003	56.7	
14	2-Aug-2004	50.5	
15	20-Aug-2005	45.5	
16	8-Aug-2006	53.6	
17	5-Aug-2007	61	
18	29-Oct-2008	65	
19	24-Jul-2009	44	
20	2-Aug-2010	53.4	
21	3-Nov-2011	47.9	
22	3-Sep-2012	37	
23	13-Oct-2013	41.2	
24	26-Aug-2014	88.1	
25	27-May-2015	33.2	
26			
27			

Figure 4-1: RF data for Maychew meteorological Station

5. Importing Excel Data

7. Currently, HEC-SSP can only import data from Excel 97-2003 Workbooks (*.xls). Use Data Import tab to import the series of annual maxima, the first step in importing data from an Excel spreadsheet is to select the browse button, at the end of the Excel File field. Once an Excel file is selected, a data view window will open showing the data contained in the selected spreadsheet.
8. Be sure to define the A, B, C, E and F parts of the data as in the example on next page, make sure E-part must be IR-YEAR, select to **Import to Study DSS file**. As you can see, a dataset has appeared in the menu on the left of the screen.

Figure 5-1: Data Importer with MS Excel Import Option Selected.

6. Plotting and Tabulating the Data

After the data is imported into the study, the user can select any one of the data sets in the study explorer. A shortcut menu will open when clicking the right mouse button while a data set is selected. The shortcut menu contains options to **change the name, plot, and tabulate** the data. These options are also available from the Data menu; however, the data must be selected in the study explorer before these options are available. If you select the **Plot** option, you will get a plot similar to the one shown in Figure 6-1.

9. If you right click on the Maychew RF Data, and select Plot, a hydrograph appears:

Figure 6-1 Plot of Peak Annual RF Data.

10. Likewise, if you hit right click on the Maychew RF Data, and select **Tabulate**, a table with the dates and RF values will open as shown in Figure 6-2. It should be noted that each year is not a calendar, but rather a hydrologic year. We are on our way to finding hydrologic extremes!

Data values in the table can be edited after selecting the **Edit>Allow Editing** menu option. To save any edits, select the **File>Save** menu option.

Ordinate	Date / Time	Maychew FLOW-PEAK Observed
Units		mm
Type		PER-AVER
1	01 Aug 1992, 24:00	54.100
2	26 Aug 1993, 24:00	92.100
3	29 Sep 1994, 24:00	68.100
4	18 Aug 1995, 24:00	58.600
5	10 Aug 1996, 24:00	51.800
6	22 Oct 1997, 24:00	30.800
7	13 May 1998, 24:00	89.500
8	16 Aug 1999, 24:00	50.800
9	28 Oct 2000, 24:00	63.000
10	18 Aug 2001, 24:00	44.300
11	05 Oct 2002, 24:00	45.500
12	25 Mar 2003, 24:00	56.700
13	01 Aug 2004, 24:00	50.500
14	19 Aug 2005, 24:00	45.500
15	07 Aug 2006, 24:00	53.600
16	04 Aug 2007, 24:00	61.000
17	28 Oct 2008, 24:00	65.000
18	23 Jul 2009, 24:00	44.000
19	01 Aug 2010, 24:00	53.400
20	02 Nov 2011, 24:00	47.900
21	02 Sep 2012, 24:00	37.000
22	12 Oct 2013, 24:00	41.200
23	25 Aug 2014, 24:00	88.100
24	26 May 2015, 24:00	33.200

Figure 6-2 Table Containing Peak Annual RF Data.

7.Performing General Frequency Analysis

With data successfully imported into the HEC-SSP program, it is ready to be analysed. The current version of HEC-SSP allows the user to perform generalized frequency analyses of flow and stage data, as well as other data types. The user can choose between different analytical distributions or perform a graphical fit to the data.

7.1 Starting a New Analysis

- General frequency analysis can be started in two ways, either by right clicking on the General Frequency Analysis folder in the study explorer and selecting **New**, or by going to the **Analysis** menu and selecting **New** and then **General Frequency Analysis**. When a new general frequency analysis is selected, the General Frequency Analysis editor will appear as shown in the Figure below.

Figure 7-1 General Frequency Analysis Editor.

- The user is required to enter a Name for the analysis, while a Description is optional. A data set (flow, stage, or other) must be selected from the available data sets stored in the current study DSS file. The list of data that can be selected for a general frequency analysis will only include those data that have an irregular interval, like IR-CENTURY and IR-YEAR (E-part pathname).

7.2 General Settings and Options

Once the analysis name and data set are selected, the user can begin to perform the computations. Contained on the General Frequency Analysis editor are four tabs. The tabs are labeled General, Options, Analytical, and Graphical. This section of the manual explains the use of the General and Options tabs.

- 13. Log Transforms;** There are two options contained within the Log Transform setting: **Use Log Transform and Do not use Log Transform.** If the user selects Use Log Transform, then the frequency analysis will be performed on the logs of the data. If the user selects Do not use Log Transform, then the frequency analysis will be performed on the raw data values without taking the logs of the data. **The default setting is Use Log Transform.**
- 14. Confidence Limits;** Confidence limits provide a measure of the uncertainty in the computed value for a given exceedance probability. By default, HEC-SSP calculates the 90 percent confidence interval (i.e. the 5% and 95% confidence limits). The user has the option to override the default values. For this exercise set the confidence limits to 95% (i.e. the 2.5% and 97.5%).
- 15. Time Window Modification;** This option allows the user to narrow the time window used for the analysis. The default is to use all of the data contained in the selected data set. The user can enter either a **start date and end date or both a start and end date.**
- 16. Data Sampling;** Two methods are available for sampling data within HEC-SSP: Partial Duration and Annual Maximum. An annual maximum series is ordinarily used when the primary interest lies in the larger events or when the second, third, fourth... nth largest event in any year is of little concern in the analysis. Conversely, a partial duration series represents the frequency of all independent events of interest, regardless of whether two or more occurred in the same year. Choosing either Partial Duration or Annual Maximum will enable and disable various other features throughout the General Frequency Analysis. **Annual Maximum is the default.**
- 17. Plotting Positions;** Plotting positions are used for plotting the raw data points on the graph. There are four options for plotting position methodologies within HEC-SSP: Weibull, Median, Hazen, and user entered coefficients. **Use The default method, Weibull plotting position formula.**

Figure 7-2. General Frequency Editor with General Settings Tab Selected.

In addition to the general settings, there are also several options available to the user for modifying the computations of the frequency curves. The following are in the options tab:

18. Low Outlier Threshold; High and low outlier tests are based on the procedures outlined in Bulletin 17B, and are applied in the same manner in the General Frequency Analysis. The calculated outlier magnitudes, by the Bulletin 17B procedure, are used as default values for the high and low outlier thresholds in HEC-SSP. The user has the option to enter a different value for the low outlier threshold, Further discussion of outlier thresholds can be found in Bulletin 17B. To use the low outlier threshold, simply check the box and enter the value.

19. Historic Period Data; All historic data that provides reliable estimates outside the systematic record should be used in order to improve the frequency computations. HEC-SSP uses historic data as recommended in Bulletin 17B. This calculation is applied in the same manner in the General Frequency Analysis. To use historic data, check the box labelled **Use Historic Data**. The user can enter a starting year for the historic period, ending year for a historic period, and a High Threshold value. If the user enters a high threshold value, then any data in the systematic record greater than that value will also be treated as a historical annual maximum. The user can also enter historic data that are not contained in the systematic record. This is done in the table at the bottom labelled **Historic Events**.

Note: The program treats all data in the data set as systematic data. If historic events are included in the data set, then the user can define the analysis time window (General tab – Time Window Modification) so that it only bounds the systematic record. Then define the historic events in the Historic Events table. Instead of using the Time Window Modification option, another option is to enter a High Threshold value so that the historic data point(s) would be treated as historic data (rather than part of the systematic record).

20. User Specified Frequency Ordinates; This option allows the user to change the frequency ordinates used in computing the resulting frequency curves and confidence limits. The default values listed in percent chance exceedance are 0.2, 0.5, 1, 2, 5, 10, 20, 50, 80, 90, 95, and 99. Check the box next to Use Values from Table below to change or add additional values. Once this box is checked, the user can add/remove rows and edit the frequency values. To add or remove a row from the table, select the row(s), place the mouse over the highlighted row(s) and click the right mouse button. The shortcut menu contains options to Insert Row(s) and Delete Row(s). The program will use the default values, even if they are not contained in the table, when the Use Values from Table below option are not checked. Finally, all values in the table must be between 0 and 100.

21. Output Labelling; This option allows the user to change the default labels for data contained in the output tables and plots. The user can change both the name of the data as well as how the units of the data are labelled.

Figure 7-3. General Frequency Editor with Options Tab Selected.

7.3 Analytical Frequency Analysis

Once the new analysis has been defined and the user has all of the general settings and options, the user can choose between performing an Analytical Frequency analysis or a Graphical Frequency analysis. This section of the manual describes how to use the Analytical Frequency analysis option.

22. When the user selects the **Analytical tab** on the General Frequency Analysis editor, the window will appear as shown in Figure 7-4. As shown, three additional tabs will appear on the screen: Settings, Tabular Results, and Plot. The Settings tab contains additional settings for the analytical frequency analysis. These settings include: Distribution, Generalized Skew, and Expected Probability Curve.

23. Distribution; This option allows the user to select from available analytical distributions to perform the frequency analysis. The current version of HEC-SSP contains three distribution choices: None, Normal, LogNormal, Pearson III, and LogPearson III. If the user has selected to transform the data to log space (General tab), then the only available choices for distribution will be None, LogNormal, and LogPearson III. If the user did not select the option to transform the data to log space (General tab), then the only available choices for distribution will be None, Normal and Pearson III. Finally, if

the user has selected to use a partial duration series on the General Tab, then no distributions will be available for use **for exercise this try to use Normal & Pearson III interchangeably.**

24. Generalized Skew; There are three options contained within the generalized skew setting: Use Station Skew, Use Weighted Skew, and Use Regional Skew. Use the default skew setting **Station Skew**. With this setting, the skew of the computed curve will be based solely on computing a skew from the data points.

25. Expected Probability Curve; This setting has two options: Compute the expected probability curve and do not compute the expected probability curve. **The default setting is to not compute the expected probability curve.** When computed, this curve will be shown in both the tables and the plots as an additional curve to the computed curve. The expected probability adjustment is a correction for bias in the computed frequency curve. The use of the expected probability curve is a policy decision. It is most often used in establishing design flood criteria. The basic flood frequency curve without the expected probability adjustment is the curve used in computation of confidence limits, risk, and in obtaining weighted averages of independent estimates of flood frequency discharge (Interagency Advisory Committee on Water Data, 1982).

Figure 7-4: Analytical Analysis Tab of the General Frequency Analysis Editor.

26. Compute; Hit Compute to determine the flood frequency curve. Then hit Plot Curve to see the flood frequency curve. If the computations are successful, the user will receive a message that says “Compute Complete”. At this point, the user can begin to review the results of the Analytical Frequency computations.

Figure 7-5: Compute General Frequency Analysis Editor.

7.4 Viewing and Printing Results

The user can view output for the frequency analysis directly from the General Frequency Analysis editor (Tabular and Graphical output) or by using the plot and view buttons at the bottom of the editor. The output consists of tabular results, an analytical frequency curve plot, a graphical frequency curve plot, and a report documenting the data and computations performed.

Plot Analytical, Graphical Curve or View report for results using the two Log distribution methods, i.e. Log Pearson Type III and Log Normal.

7.4.1 Tabular Results

Once the computations for the analytical frequency analysis are completed, the user can view tabular output by selecting the Tabular Results tab under the Analytical analysis tab.

The tabular results can be printed by using the Print button at the bottom of the General Frequency Analysis editor. When the print button is pressed, a window will appear giving the user options for how they would like the table to be printed.

27. As shown in Figure 7-6, the window contains three tables. The top table contains results of the computed frequency curve. The very left column of the top table is the Percent Chance Exceedance for all the computed values. The next three columns in the top table contain the computed frequency curve and the 95% and 5% confidence limits that correspond to that computed curve. The last three columns of the top table contain a computed frequency curve and confidence limits for an analysis based on user-adjusted statistics for the mean, standard deviation, adopted skew, and equivalent years of record. User entered adjusted statistics are an option that the user can set on the **Plot** tab, If the user has not entered adjusted statistics, then these columns will be empty. Data in the frequency curve table can be re-sorted. Click the **Percent Chance Exceedance** column header (two mouse clicks are required the first time). The percent chance exceedance ordinates, along with frequency curve and confidence limits values, will sort so that the lowest values are on top or the highest values are on top.

- 28. Two additional tables are shown at the bottom of the window: Statistics and Number of Events. The **Statistics** table consists of the mean, standard deviation, station skew, user entered regional skew, weighted skew (weighted between station skew and regional skew), and the adopted skew for the analysis. The **Number of Events** table contains the number of historic events, high outliers, low outliers, zero or missing values, systematic events, and the number of years in the historic period (this value only comes into play if the user entered historic data).
- 29. Additionally, the lower right portion of the table will show if Log Transform is On or Off, and which analytical distribution was selected for the analysis.

Figure 7-6: Tabular Results Tab for Analytical Analysis.

7.4.3 Graphical Output

In addition to tabular results, a **Plot** tab is available for viewing a graphical plot of both the computed frequency curve, as well as a computed curve based on any user-adjusted statistics. When the **Plot** tab is selected the window will change to what is shown in Figure 7-7. As shown in Figure 7-7, the plot contains the computed frequency curve, 95% and 5% confidence limits, and raw data points plotted by the user selected plotting position method.

The computed statistics for the frequency curve are shown in a table on the right side of the window. Below the computed statistics is a table labeled "User Statistics". There is a check box and a data entry field for the Mean, Standard Deviation, Adopted Skew, and Equivalent Years of Record. The user can enter values into any or all of these fields. The user statistics option allows the user to see how the curve would change if any or all of the statistics were different. When data is entered into the user statistics fields, and the check boxes are turned on, the user must press the compute button again in order for the computations to be performed with the user entered statistics. After the compute button is pressed, both the plot and the table on the Tabular Results tab will be updated to reflect any user entered statistics.

- 30. Graphical output of the analytical frequency curve can be obtained by selecting either the Plot tab under the analytical analysis tab, or by pressing the button labeled Plot Analytical Curve at the bottom of the general frequency editor. When the Plot Analytical Curve button is pressed, a frequency curve plot will appear in a separate window as shown in Figure 7-7. The analytical frequency curve plot can be sent to the printer by selecting the Print option from the File menu at the top of the window. Additional printing options available from the File menu are Page Setup, Print Preview, and Print Multiple (used for printing multiple graphs on the same page).

Figure 7-7: Plot Tab of the General Frequency Analytical Analysis.

7.4.3 Viewing the Report File

When the General Frequency analysis computations are performed, a report file of the statistical computations is created. The report file lists all of the input data and user settings, plotting positions of the data points, intermediate results, each of the various statistical tests performed (i.e. high and low outliers, historical data, etc...), and the final results. This file is often useful for understanding and describing how the software arrived at the final frequency curve.

31. To view the report file, press the View Report button at the bottom of the General Frequency analysis editor. When this button is pressed, a window will appear containing the report as shown in Figure 7-8. Plots, tables, and reports can also be created by selecting menu options from the Results menu. At least one General Frequency analysis must be selected in the study explorer before selecting one of the menu options on the **Results** menu.

Figure 7-8: General Frequency Analysis Report File.

7.6 Summary Results (Design Storm)

To see the results of the General Frequency Analysis from the tabular results, computed design storms associated with required return period, with both distributions together with the upper and lower percent confidence intervals (i.e. 0.05 and 0.95). are summered as follows.

Table 7-1: Design Storm Summary

Distribution Type	Log Pearson III			Log Normal		
	Design Discharge Q_T	95% Confidence Interval (Upper) Q_T^U	95% Confidence Interval (Lower) Q_T^L	Design Discharge Q_T	95% Confidence Interval (Upper) Q_T^U	95% Confidence Interval (Lower) Q_T^L
(Years)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)	(mm)
50	89.4	132.9	73.5			
100	98.5	154.8	79.2			
200	108	179.1	84.9			
500	121.3	215.6	92.7			
1000	132	246.9	98.7			